

Reading and the brain: What teachers ought to know and how they can help children with problems in word recognition

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Abstract

Reading as a process is best understood if we look at it in the context of its neural pathways that have been identified through several studies using the focal magnetic resonance imaging. In this paper, the author discusses the three neural pathways for reading: two slower, analytic ones (i.e., parieto-temporal and inferior frontal gyrus or Broca's area) used by beginning or novice readers, and an express route (i.e., occipito-temporal) used by experienced, skilled readers. He has also gone on to discuss what teachers should know about these three reading routes and what they can do to help children with problems in word recognition.

Key words: *Brain, Cortical Areas, Neural Pathways, Reading, Reading Routes*

Introduction

Although both speaking and reading involve phonological processing, the former is natural; the latter is not. Studies (e.g., Kripke, 2004; Leung & Kao, 2001; Toppelberg & Shapiro, 2000) have shown that speech delay can impact on reading, resulting in specific language impairment (Chia & Poh, 2009) and specific learning difficulties such as dyslexia. According to the information processing model of reading (see Figure 1 on the next page), a reading text can come in the form of a visual (e.g., comics) or auditory (e.g., an audio-tape) format that provides sensory input to be engaged by a reader through either the visual (sight) / auditory (aural) receptor or both.

These sensory data are then taken up by the working memory (also known as the conscious state of mind) (Markova & Powell, 1992), separated into either visual-spatial or auditory-sequential information for processing before being transferred to the short-term memory (also known as the subconscious state of mind) (Markova & Powell, 1992), which in turn plays an important role in schema-matching the new information received from the reading text with the reader's prior knowledge and background experience retrieved from the long-term memory (also known as the unconscious state of mind) (Markova & Powell, 1992) to build a textual meaning in order to achieve comprehension of what is read, and lastly, to respond to the text by either reading silently or aloud. Answering correctly to comprehension questions is also a form of responding with appropriate sensory output (e.g., oral or written response).

Figure 1: Information Processing Model of Reading

Interrelated Sequential Sub-processes of Reading

In other words, there are five interrelated sequential sub-processes that take place within the reading process: (1) receiving incoming environmental sensory data (e.g., conversation and print as in speech and reading respectively); (2) decoding that takes place in the working/short-term memory; (3) building meaning through schema-matching between the sensory data received and prior knowledge/background experience; (4) establishing comprehension; and (5) responding with appropriate sensory output (e.g., silent reading and reading aloud). Each of these sequential processes will be briefly described below:

(1) Receiving environmental sensory data

The way a reader responds to environmental sensory data such as, audio-story tapes (e.g., *The Storyteller II*), e-journals, pop-up books and printed materials (e.g., books and periodicals) determines what information gets his/her attention and in what mode that best captures that attention. Hence, not all readers prepare to engage printed material. Others may prefer listening

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to audio-tapes of motivational talks or sermons or audio-books of favourite classics such as *Black Beauty* and *The Treasure Island*.

According to Willis (2008), whichever mode a reader chooses to receive the incoming sensory input, only selected information passes through his/her lower brain filter known as reticular activating system (RAS) to enter his/her thinking brain. This is the attention-activation switching system of the brain stem, which is located at the lower back of the brain. It is the RAS that sets the mental state of arousal and vigilance for the brain. It also selectively alerts the brain to the environmental changes that impact its survival, i.e., sound, sight, taste, touch, and smell that may indicate danger or signal opportunities to find food for an example.

Messages from the RAS are transmitted to another important part of the brain called thalamus, which “sits on top of the brain stem and is shaped into two lobes” (Giles, 2002, p.25). It is the receiving point for all incoming sensory data (with the exception of smell), and its function is to act as a sort of relay station, transmitting neural messages to the appropriate parts of the cortex for further processing (Wolfe & Nevills, 2008). In the case of sound stimulus (e.g., listening to a narrative audio-tape), the aural sensory input is sent to the primary auditory cortex, which is located in the front of the temporal lobe of the brain. The thalamus and the primary auditory cortex appear to work in concert to determine if the incoming stimulus is language, music or random noise from the environment. Once the aural data have been identified as language, the neural message is transmitted to Wernicke’s area.

(2) Decoding

Decoding is a cognitive process that involves word recognition (for known or familiar words) and/or word identification (for new or unknown words), and it can be further divided into two cognitive sub-processes (Chia, 2006): (a) aural-visual decoding for word recognition and silent reading; and (b) visual-oral decoding for word expression and reading aloud.

Findings from past and current brain research studies (e.g., Bloom, Nelson, & Lazerson, 2001; Dejerine, 1891; Shaywitz, 2003) have found that most of the reading part of the brain takes place in the back known as the posterior reading system, which is made up of two different pathways for reading words, one sitting somewhat higher in the brain than the other (see Figure 2). The higher one (indicated by a red arrow) is the parieto-temporal decoding route while the lower one (indicated by a blue arrow) is the occipito-temporal decoding route.

Figure 2: The Posterior Reading System

Key:

1 = Parietal-temporal area (for word analysis); 2 = Occipito-temporal area (instantaneous word recognition/identification); 3 = Broca's area (for articulation and word analysis); 4 = somato-motor cortex (motor activities); 5 = somato-sensory cortex (sensory activities)

The upper pathway is located primarily in the middle of the brain known as the parieto-temporal region, which covers the language cortex (including Wernicke's area), sensory association cortex and sensory cortex (Giles, 2002). The parietal lobe processes spatial information of the words in an advanced way, such as the creation of mental images of letters found in words and recognition or identification of words encountered during reading. The function of this first reading pathway – known as letter-sound association reading system – though slow and analytic, seems to be in the early stages of learning to read, i.e., segmenting a word into its phonemic constituents.

In contrast, the lower pathway runs closer to the bottom of the brain where two lobes of the brain – the occipital and the temporal – converge and referred to as the occipito-temporal area, which covers primary visual cortex, visual association cortex and language cortex (Giles, 2002). This is the word-form reading system that serves to react almost instantly to recognize the whole word as a pattern. These two subsystems have different roles in reading, and their functions make sense in the changing needs of the reader (see Figure 2).

According to Shaywitz (2003), there is a third reading pathway (indicated by a green arrow) that involves Broca's area (found in the frontal lobe of the brain) which also helps in slowly analyzing a word. According to Preen and Barker (1986), lesions in Broca's area could result in comprehension of printed text being severely impaired and hence, also affecting the reading process. Older children with dyslexia “show increased activities in frontal regions so that by adolescence they are demonstrating a pattern of over-activities in Broca's area, i.e., they are increasingly using these frontal regions for reading” (p.81). As a result, these children

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compensate their reading difficulty by sub-vocalization (i.e., ‘mouth’ word for word aloud) as they read, a process that utilizes Broca’s area which is responsible for articulating spoken words. This process of sub-vocalization allows these children to read, albeit more slowly than if the left posterior systems were working.

In other words, this is a response initiated by the brain as a kind of compensatory strategy to aid reading comprehension. “Sounds heard from reading aloud are received by the ears via auditory nerves to the primary auditory cortex for word analysis before directing the analyzed information to Wernicke’s area to match its corresponding meaning. The word meanings from Wernicke’s area are conveyed to Broca’s area” (Chia, 1992, p.35).

As a reader with dyslexia tried to sound out words, the brain images through magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) show that posterior system on the left hemisphere of the brain is disrupted or not working; instead, the alternate secondary pathways (not a repair but a different route) to reading are used. In addition to greater reliance on Broca’s area, other right hemispheric auxiliary systems for reading in the frontal lobe function to allow for accurate, albeit very slow, reading (Shaywitz, 2003).

Hence, there are three neural pathways for reading: “two slower, analytic ones (i.e., parieto-temporal and inferior frontal gyrus or Broca’s area) used by beginning or novice readers, and an express route (i.e., occipito-temporal) used by experienced, skilled readers” (Shaywitz, 2003, p.79).

(3) Building meaning

Meanings of words are processed by the brain in Wernicke’s area – the group of neurons located at the junction of the parietal and temporal lobes in the left hemisphere very near to the primary auditory cortex. Major language structures are located in this part of the brain (Restak, 2001).

Research studies (e.g., Carter, 1998; Penfield & Roberts, 1959; Wolfe & Nevills, 2008) suggest that Wernicke’s area contains a mental lexicon that stores memories of the sounds that make up words. It uses this mental resource to assess if the incoming phonemic patterns are meaningful words or nonsensical non-words (Chia, 1992). People with brain damage to this particular area show no speech difficulty, but their spoken language makes no sense to anyone who listens to what they are talking. According to Carter (1998) and Wolfe and Nevills (2008), these people are also unable to monitor their own speech, do not seem to be conscious that they are substituting non-words for real ones, and that to a listener much of what they are saying is meaningless. In other words, spoken sentences are well formed syntactically but devoid of meaning (Fromkin et al., 1984). This is known as Wernicke’s aphasia.

(4) Establishing comprehension

Comprehension, the essence of reading (Durkin, 1993), “is often taken to mean reading comprehension in the literacy literature unless restricted specifically or by inference from its context” (Harris & Hodges, 1995, p.38). According to Chia (1996), comprehension can be categorized into five levels beginning with literal, reorganizational, inferential, critical/evaluative, and appreciative. The first two levels of comprehension are often associated with reading the

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lines; the third one is reading between the lines; and the last two levels as reading beyond the lines.

Wernicke's area "plays a significant role in the conscious comprehension of spoken words by both the listener and the speaker" (Wolfe & Nevills, 2008, p.255). Comprehension of what we listen or read depends on the proper functioning of the Wernicke's area. People with Wernicke's aphasia display a severe difficulty in understanding what others are saying to them.

(5) Responding with appropriate sensory output

The last phase of the reading process is the reader's appropriate response to the reading stimulus. This can take place in form of either silent or oral reading. Reading aloud can serve as a form of comprehension monitoring – an act of "noting one's successes and failures in developing or attaining meaning, usually with reference to an emerging conception of the meaning of the text as a whole, and adjusting one's reading process accordingly" (Harris & Hodges, 1995, p.39).

Translating into Pedagogical Application

As mentioned earlier, there are three neural pathways for reading:

1. parieto-temporal decoding route;
2. frontal (Broca's area) decoding route; and
3. occipito-temporal decoding route.

The first two decoding routes offer a slower reading process that involves word analysis that is used mainly by beginning or novice readers. The third decoding route is an express reading process relied on by experienced, skilled readers. Teachers and allied educators should be concerned if their children are using the first two decoding routes in their reading. The question they need to ask now is how they can help these children.

Translating the theoretical knowledge of how the brain works in the reading process into pedagogical application is essential for teachers/allied educators if they are to understand how to use what they have learnt to teach word recognition. Let us first begin with the parieto-temporal decoding route, also known as the letter-sound association reading pathway (Shaywitz, 2003) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Parieto-temporal decoding route

In this slow, analytic route of reading, a word is first perceived by its configuration or shape and is then analyzed by breaking it down into its constituents in order to be recognized (for familiar words to be confirmed) or identified (for new/unfamiliar words to be learnt). Word recognition is best taught through onset-rime for this form of decoding. Onset is that part of a syllable preceding the syllable peak and is normally, the consonants preceding the vowel of a syllable, as **b** in **bat**, **st** in **stop**, and **sch** in **school**. Rime consists of a vowel and any following consonants of a syllable, as **-ool** in **pool**, and **-ag** in **bag**.

The second slow, analytic route of reading is the frontal (Broca's area) decoding route (see Figure 4). The main difference between this second one and the earlier one is that the frontal decoding route involves sub-vocalization, which is a form of compensatory behavior to cope with some reading difficulty (as in a child with dyslexia). Like the parieto-temporal decoding route, the frontal decoding route also involves word analysis except that the reader sub-vocalizes first in an attempt to analyze the word in order to recognize it (for familiar words to be confirmed) or identify it (for new/unfamiliar words to be learnt). Listening to what he/she has sub-vocalized is a way to evaluate the aural feedback as a form of self-checking before the reader says the word aloud as in oral reading. Hence, the process is slow and tedious.

Figure 4: Frontal decoding route

In taking this route of reading, the reader has possessed some phonological awareness but his/her phonological knowledge is either inadequate or incomplete. The best approach to help such a reader in word recognition is to teach him/her synthetic phonics. Harris and Hodges (1995) have defined this form of phonics as “a part-to-whole phonics approach to reading instruction in which the student learns the sounds represented by letters and letter combinations, blends these sounds to pronounce words, and finally identifies which phonic generalization apply” (p.250). It is also known as inductive phonics (Chia, 2003). For more information about inductive or

synthetic phonics, interested readers can refer to the book *Teaching Tips for teachers and Parents of Preschoolers and Primary School Children* edited by E.L. Low and N. Suzanne (2003) and published by the Society for Reading and Literacy.

Figure 5 below shows the occipito-temporal decoding route, which is also known as word-form reading system that serves to respond almost instantly to recognize the whole word as a pattern. This is the fluent reading pathway that an experienced, skilled reader will take. Children, who are already using this decoding route, are doing fine in their reading. There is nothing parents and teachers need to worry them about except to provide good literature with strong support and encouragement.

Figure 5: Occipito-temporal decoding route

Conclusion

In summary, this brief article aims to introduce findings from brain research to teachers, allied educators and parents to help them know and understand how the different parts of our brain work during each of the three different reading pathways and to suggest an appropriate approach to teach word recognition. It is important for me to mention here that the various diagrams (i.e., Figures 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) that I have used to illustrate the functions of the three decoding routes should not be in any way be regarded as a realistic picture of any area (e.g., Broca's area and Wernicke's area) it is attempting to represent. In all the diagrams, boxes and pictures have been used, but they could equally well have been shown as circles or any other shapes. Their purpose is to provide an analogy, and the exact representation is a matter of convenience.

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